

CERTIFICATE

OF APPRECIATION

TIBBIYOT AKADEMIYASI

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Odiljonov Javokhirmirzo Dilmurodzhan ugli

THE USE OF ORTHOPEDIC CONSTRUCTIONS IN THE PREVENTION OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES

**NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI**

WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

